

Digital Finance: The Concept and Emergence with reference to academic affairs

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Abstract

The concept and term Digital Finance is important and valuable in current age. In generally it is the application of Information Technology and Computing in Financial affairs. The field is closely associated with the Banking, Commerce, Management and Economics. The term Financial Technology is also closely associated with the Digital Finance. Digital finance is an advance concept to move healthy and modern financial services in difference sectors viz. agriculture, transportation, healthcare, tourism education etc. Digital finance is responsible for the greater financial inclusion; it is also responsible and dedicated for the expansion of basic services. It is a fact that today more than 50% community in the developing world having their own a mobile phone and thus the concept of Digital Finance is increasing and importantly the challenge is massive because 2.5 billion individuals may have problem in digital fiancé inclusion. It is worthy to note that about 200 million small businesses is also have bad access to basic financial services due to various services. Country like India also has various other problems e.g. India has about 155,000 post offices and majority are in rural areas and thus they are playing a critical role in enhancing financial inclusion, and indirectly these are responsible for the financial services which include banking, insurance etc. It is a fact that due to the importance of Digital Finance many universities in the world has started the program in Digital Finance not only in Certificate level but also in Masters level. This paper is talks about the basics of Digital Finance and its educational affairs also. Paper highlighted the emerging areas also.

Keywords:Digital Finance, Education, Business Information Systems, Emerging Technology, Business Promotion, Developed Country

Introduction

The world is moving towards best in digitalization and computerizations. Business and Finance is now become integral part of technology [2], [11]. Digital Finance is about applications of different kind of Information Technology components on Finance and similar affairs and among these components few important are include—

- Networking Technology
- Web Technology
- Multimedia Technology
- Software Technology
- Database Technology and allied

Financial affairs are including various direct and indirect issues on business, insurance and banking. The term Digital Finance not only now a concept but also a field of study and in some context an emerging area of research and development affairs [1], [5].

Digital financial inclusion is an important term and as digital access uses formal financial services by excluded and underserved populations and importantly such kind of concepts and services suited to the customers' needs and delivered with affordable cost to customers and sustainable for providers (*The core IT components of Digital Finance is depicted in Fig: 1*).

Fig: 1-Depicted basic components of IT and vis-à-vis Digital Finance

It is worthy to note that 200 million small businesses are also have bad access to basic financial services and nation like India also has various other problems. In recent past India done much better in small financial sectors and there Digital Finance play a great role. Moreover, India has about 155,000 post offices and majority are in rural areas and thus they are playing a critical role in enhancing financial inclusion empowered by IT and Computing technologies [2], [3].

Objective

The core aim and agenda of this paper is including (but not limited to the following)—

- To learn about the basics of Digital Finance and similar and allied areas of Digital Finance.
- To know about the characteristics of Digital Finance and similar domain/ fields in brief manner.
- To know about the stakeholders and gradients of Digital Finance and similar areas in brief.
- To learn about the academic program on Digital Finance and allied areas available in International universities and higher educational institutions.

Digital Finance and its Inclusion: Digital Financial Inclusion

Today Digital Finance play a leading role in better customer relationship management; n generally following four function are treated as most important and valuable for the Digital Finance Inclusion—

- A full-service bank offering a “basic” or “simplified” transactional affairs leading to payments and similar affairs.
- A limited-service based systems for the account via mobile device or any other electronic payment card systems.
- Important issue is mobile network operator (MNO) e-money issue for better and healthy Digital Finance inclusion.
- A nonbank and non-MNO e-money issue for sustainable Digital Finance inclusion.

These 4 functions normally work by the three components and these are include the *first one*, Digital transactional platform the *second one*, An agent network and the *third* one client access device [6], [7]. Here in all sorts, place, payments, transfer, credit, savings and insurance etc play a leading and great role. The Fig: 2 depicted the core stakeholders in Digital Finance at a glance.

Fig: 2-Stakeholders in Digital Finance

Digital Finance and Educational Programs

The Development in Digital Financial and Management systems is growing rapidly internationally and as a result various university have been started program in the field of Digital Finance and allied areas, according to the study it has been noted that many universities started offering program on this with Masters Degrees [4], [8], [12]. The study employed in this work is use of simple Google search engine with the title ‘Master in Digital Finance’ and there ten (10) page results has been analyzed and reported in this work. Apart from the Digital Finance, following areas have been identified in this study and these include—

- Digital Currency
- Digital Marketing
- Digital Business
- Digital Innovation

Importantly, these results have been opted by only using the adopted search strategy and there are numerous programs also may be find-out by using different course/ nomenclature. The result of top ten pages on the required subjects is depicted in Table: 1.

Table: 1-Digital Finance and allied programs (few popular)

Sl. No.	Name of the Program	Institute/ University	Country
1	Masters in Management (Digital Business)	HEC, Paris	France
2	MSc-Digital Marketing & Data Science	EMLYON Business School	France
3	MSc- Digital Currency	University of Nicosia	Cyprus
4	Masters in Financial Management, Digital Banking and Internet Finance	Global Business School, Barcelona	Spain
5	MSc-Data Analytics and Digital Business	EDHEC Business School	France
6	MSc-Digital Innovation	UCD Graduate Business School	Ireland

It has been studied that, most of the programs are offered in the European countries and leading nation in this regard is France. It is also worthy to note that most of the program are also offered in the School/ College/ Department of Business or Management instead of IT or Computing related department.

Digital Finance and Possible Educational Programs: Indian Context

Internationally universities played a lead role for the development of the domain Digital Finance, as far as India is concerned only a few institutes have started the program on the subject with the nomenclature of Certificate / Diploma. Though not single institutes have started the program at Bachelors or Masters levels.

India is one of the large education systems in the world with more than 40000+ Higher Educational Institutes offering Bachelors to Doctoral Degrees and there are huge intake capacity. As far as Digital Finance and allied areas the field may be offered in allied stream as a Major/ Specialization with the Subject like Management/ Business Administration,

Commerce. Even in Information Technology also. Some of the possible specialized program in Digital Finance and allied areas are depicted in Table: 2 and Table: 3 respectively.

Table: 2-Digital Finance and allied programs (few popular)

Sl. No.	Possible Bachelors Program (Commerce Track)	Possible Masters Program (Commerce Track)
1	B.Com (Digital Finance)	M.Com (Digital Finance)
2	B.Com (Digital Finance and Business)	M.Com (Digital Finance and Business)
3	B.Com (Digital Finance and Big Data)	M.Com (Digital Finance and Big Data)
4	B.Com (Big Data and Financial Market)	M.Com (Big Data and Financial Market)
5	B.Com (Financial Technology)	M.Com (Financial Technology)
6	B.Com (Business & Financial Informatics)	M.Com (Business & Financial Informatics)

Whereas in Table: 3 Digital Marketing and allied areas have been proposed with Management and Business Studies context.

Table: 2-Digital Finance and allied programs (few popular)

Sl. No.	Possible Bachelors Program (Management Track)	Possible Masters Program (Management Track)
1	BBA/ BBM (Digital Finance)	MBA/ MMA (Digital Finance)
2	BBA/ BBM (Digital Finance and Business)	MBA/MMA (Digital Finance and Business)
3	BBA/ BBM (Digital Finance and Big Data)	MBA/ MMA (Digital Finance and Big Data)

Conclusion

The areas and stakeholders in the field of Digital Finance and allied areas are increasing and growing rapidly. Many universities internationally have designed and developed various programs in this field for providing right and adequate manpower in the field [9], [10], [13]. Developed nations already done various initiatives and activities in this space and in

developing nations various initiatives. Indian Universities and business and commercial venture can develop joint program in the field with other concentration leading to Arts, Science and Technology etc. As Financial affairs are including various direct and indirect issues on business, insurance and banking thus the concept is emerging and growing rapidly.

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